

Religious Ethical Values as Requisite for National Integration

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Abstract

It is a veritable fact that Nigeria is a pluralistic and multi-religious nation with Christianity, Islam and African Traditional Religion dominating the religious space. In spite of the high moral traditions maintained by these religions; the country has been cut in the web of moral decadence which has become voracious and alarming during the past two decades, threatening nearly every stratum of the society. It is within this context that the study examined the place of religious ethical values and the quest for national integration in a country with high propensity for religion. Data was generated through existing literature and by careful observation of the current state of the nation. The data collected was subjected to ethical analysis. The study discovered that there is consistent religiosity without corresponding morality among Nigerian peoples. The inability of religious adherents to utilize the core ethical values of discipline, loyalty, justice, accountability and honesty as well as other positive values derivable from their religions can be attributed as the principal factor working against national integration and development in Nigeria. The paper thus recommended that the religious peoples of Nigeria must champion the course of restoring religious ethical values in Nigeria based on their religious faith and practice. The paper concluded that religious ethical values if properly harnessed have the potentials to influence the country's socio-economic and religio-political structures that will not only bring about moral sanity but ensure an axiological panacea to the nation's quest for national integration.

Keywords: Religion, Ethical Values, National Integration

Introduction

Religion over the years has assumed various forms and stages in human society. This depends on the cultural, intellectual and spiritual growth of every nation, race or ethnic community. Human beings are religious and this natural tendency can be seen in the way many things are often conceived and done. Human religiosity is often manifested in songs, folktales, proverbs, myths, communication (oral and written).¹ According to Akpenpuun, religion contributes immensely to the maintenance of order and national integration by creating conditions for social well-being, discipline, social solidarity, social cohesion, peace and unity.² To state the obvious, religion given its high values and moral codes influences the whole life and activity of the religious person, society or nation. Where this is not obtainable, then there is a lacuna in the right practice of religion.

Generally, it is believed that religious ethical values are God centred given the assumption that it originates from God. This suggests that God is the source of religious ethics. This is expressed within the belief that God is the maker of the earth and everything there including man morality.³ The teachings and injunctions of the Holy Books all affirm this. For example, the Bible declares that: "All scripture is God-breathed and is useful for teaching, rebuking, correcting and training in righteousness so that the man of God may be thoroughly equipped for every good work" (2 Timothy 3:16-17 NIV). Similarly, the Qu'ran is Al-Burhan 'the proof' and Al-Furqan 'the distinction'. It is a distinction between the truth and falsehood, right and wrong... it is a complete code of life. It represents clearly the intellectual and moral bases of Islamic Shari'ah and strengthens them with arguments and appeals to the heart. Again, religious ethical values also rest on some established and institutionalized

traditions which clearly provide the acceptable course of actions. In traditional region we have oral traditions which are stories, folktales, myths and fables passed in oral form from one generation to another.⁴ All these put together define the course of action of every religious person in any given environment and time. The codes and values derivable from religious ethics are meant to be practiced by religious people anywhere they may find themselves.

One fundamental social reality about the Nigerian state is that, majority of her citizens are very religious. In fact, so many Nigerians believe that anybody who does not proclaim or practice any form of religion is seriously in need of help. Another social reality about this country is the gross perversion of morality that is almost becoming a norm in nearly every stratum of the society. One big task before every rational mind in Nigeria is how to reconcile the extreme religiosity of her citizens with the overwhelming moral decay in the country.

According to Ochulor and Bassey, the prevalence of corruption betrays a latent decay in Nigeria's ethical values and orientation. It shows the futile attempt by Nigerians to build a nation-state without a foundational reference to the religious moral principles of justice, transparency, altruism, accountability and a service-oriented notion of leadership.⁵ In his view, Obasola contends that Nigeria has experienced and is still experiencing its share of moral laxity and vices especially as depicted in political instability, corruption in high and low places, drug trafficking, smuggling, advanced fee fraud commonly known as 419, prostitution, increasing crime wave, theft, robbery, religious and ethnic violence, unemployment, injustice, terrorism, kidnapping, alms begging among others. It is no longer news that Nigeria is labeled as one of the countries with a very high rate of corruption and moral decadence among the comity of nations in the global social space. The Nigerian story has been a paradox. A nation with a lot of potentials yet unfulfilled. A nation so blessed with abundant human and natural resources yet trapped in avoidable poverty, inequality, injustice, leadership failure, resource mismanagement, chronic under-development as well as misplaced priorities and values.⁶

It is imperative to state that Nigeria is a highly religious country. The three major religions featuring prominently in Nigeria are; Christianity, Islam and African Traditional Religion. These three religious traditions have similar fundamental moral values such as discipline, loyalty, justice, honesty, trustworthiness, integrity, transparency, accountability, hard-work, diligence, altruism and others as basic tenets of their theological doctrines. Unfortunately, many adherents of these religions, especially Islam and Christianity in Nigeria have continued to engage themselves in some corrupt activities that contradict the aforementioned lofty moral values.

In the contemporary times, corrupt practices and other forms of moral bankruptcy have become so pronounced in different areas of personal and public life such as, religious worship, business transaction, political and judicial administration, employer-employee relationship, family life, among others in the Nigerian state. There is a widespread perception that the general populace and the political elites who are from one religion or another have all lost their moral compass and that avarice and the love for materialism have become the overriding principles governing how religious worships, social and political activities are conducted in the country.⁷ This very well means that corruption is not only endemic but systematically thriving on the shoulders of those who are supposed to fight it, while the rest of the population watches in gross misery.

The term corruption in Nigerian context is all encompassing as it refers not only to the abuse of state offices for some kind of private gain but also to a whole range of social behaviour that raise moral questions about the achievement of one's education, wealth, power, employment, justice as well as more mundane ambitions. The Nigerian notion of corruption includes everything from bribery and graft, rigged elections, insecurity, fraudulent business and contract deals, to the diabolical manipulations of occult powers, medical quackery, examination malpractice etc.⁸ Today, the negative tendencies of greed, selfishness, licentiousness, covetousness, lust, pride, materialism, envy, wickedness, war-mongering, callousness, and other forms of moral mishaps are gradually becoming a norm in the Nigerian socio-religious space.⁹ The prime motive of this research therefore is to answer the question of why Nigeria has come under the onslaught of such moral vices that are brewing up tension, conflicts and acrimony in a country with such lofty moral values inherent in the theological doctrines of the three main religions being practiced in the country.

Towards a Conceptualization

Values: Values are thoughts, habits and actions that are most cherished and held with high esteem in society. Values defines what is important, worthwhile and worth striving for in the society.¹⁰ In a more elaborate manner, Halstead and Taylor sees values as: “Principles and fundamental convictions which acts as general guides to behaviour, enduring beliefs about what is worthwhile, ideals for which one strives, standards by which particular beliefs and actions are judged to be good or desirable.”¹¹ According to Obasola, values are those intrinsic attributes and characteristics which are innate in every person for the actualization and promotion of social order, cohesion and peaceful coexistence which are fundamental indices for growth and development in the society.¹²

This very well means that values are those essential determinants in an individual’s perception of what is good and desirable in the society. Edeth maintains that values have to do with truthfulness, patience, obedience, love, peace, honesty, integrity, hard work, responsibility, respect, tolerance, loyalty, public spiritedness, freedom, respect for human life and dignity of persons, justice, fairness, equality among others are part and parcel of our human identity toward which societies and people strive or evolved.¹³ Values share the same meaning with morality since both terms seeks after a pattern of conduct that is desired and acceptable by the society.¹⁴ On that note, Debbarma explains that “Values are generally regarded as the moral standards of human behaviours in the society. It is a kind of quality in humans which is applied to all human activities. It is transmitted to a circumstantial factor which depends upon the judgment of facts.”¹⁵ This is indicative of the fact that the evaluation of good and evil, right or wrong, legitimate or illegitimate is based on the values of each individual or organization. Values can be either a starting point or a target to pursue, an idea to be implemented and a goal to achieve. Therefore, people whose fundamental beliefs, orientations and evaluations are rooted in resounding values have a clear sense of right and wrong. Their moral code is not based on how they feel; rather it is founded on a firm set of principles that act as a guide for conduct-even when they are not being supervised.

Religious Ethical Values: Religious ethical values are a set of institutionalized ideals which guide and direct the patterns of life of religious adherents.¹⁶ It is incumbent on all religious people to exhibit good character and to embrace social actions that are praiseworthy, altruistic and morally sound. This is because religion frowns at all forms of vices and immoral behaviours. Religion is seen as the foundation of morality and values wherein all vices are punished and virtues rewarded accordingly. According to Ali, it is generally believed that the divinities supervise the activities of their worshippers and the worshippers in turn are careful to obey the moral demands of their divinities.¹⁷ This then suggests that morality is a fundamental constituent of religion, given that the fear of God and adherence to his commands are regarded as the source or foundation of values in religions. According to Edeth, the fear of God and adherence to his commands yield religious systems. These religious systems provide the basis or foundation of certain moral values.¹⁸

The foundation of values here is considered to be divine revelation. A fundamental part of any religious system is in its moral values which regulate and harmonize human life. In many societies of the world, religion has continued to serve as mechanism which reminds people of what is right and what is wrong; what is good and what is evil, what is just and what is a vice. In essence, religion has continued to enrich people’s morals for the welfare of individuals and the society at large. In his assertion, Ayantayo says in the context of religion, human ethical or moral values such as truth-telling, honesty, justice and impartiality, become commands issued by the supernatural being. For example, God in Christianity, Allah in Islam and Obatala or Aondo in Yoruba and Tiv Traditional Religion becomes the great moral lawgiver.¹⁹ In essence, the divine command makes the human moral standards punishable directly by divine authorities.

In sum therefore, religious ethical values are those essential principles that guide people’s lives in terms of their thoughts, decisions and preferences which can be measured and judged to be worthwhile. Religious values are mostly important, because they are regarded as belonging to a superior level. They cannot be replaced so easily; they are not negotiable, and they are at the same time highly desirable. That is the reason why individuals are prepared to make sacrifices and to go through all sorts of difficulties for them.

National Integration: First and foremost, the word ‘integration’, literally means assembling parts into a whole.²⁰ It could be argued that integration is a progressive removal of antagonisms and reduction of cultural and regional attachments and differences in the process of creating a homogenous society. In a pluralistic society such as Nigeria, there is need to foster integration for a harmonious co-existence here in called ‘national integration’. National integration refers to the process of bringing diverse cultural and social groups into a single territorial unit and the establishment of a national unity.²¹ What this portends is that national integration constitutes the conscious strategy for achieving social stability and social progress. The term presumes the existence of an ethnically plural society in which each group is characterized by its own language, or other self-conscious cultural qualities, which generate the problem of creating a sense of territorial nationality, which overshadows or eliminates subordinate parochial loyalties. From the foregoing, national integration refers to the process of building a just social unit which confers on every inhabitant within it a sense of belonging, a satisfactory level of participation in decision-making and development and a change to share from the resources of the society commensurate with decent and acceptable living standard.

Ethical Reflection on the Moral State of the Nation

The three major religions in Nigeria—African Traditional Religion, Islam and Christianity are embodiments of moral values. A glimpse at their theological doctrines reveal that moral principles such as, service oriented leadership, dignity of labour, accountability, transparency, loyalty, truthfulness, honesty, trustworthiness, integrity, diligence, righteousness, faithfulness, social justice, covenant keeping, social solidarity, altruism, patriotism and others, are the core values of these religions. It is pertinent to state at this point that an overwhelming majority of Nigerian citizens are adherents of Christianity and Islam, with only very few people still proudly practicing African Traditional Religion. Majority of the people at the helm of affairs in the various sectors of the country’s socio-political and economic domain where most of the corrupt practices are thriving are practicing religious people.

It has been observed with pain and deep displeasure the steep decline in morals and values among religious adherents in Nigeria across all faiths and cultures, which is largely responsible for the corruption, violence and decadence been experienced in the Nigerian socio-political and economic space. There are evidences of massive corruption, poverty, violence, crime and pain in different sectors of the Nigerian society because those religious members of the society are failing to manifest the moral values inherent in their religious doctrines which they cherish or admire while performing public functions.²² This is clearly seen in the attitudes and acts of misconducts of some Nigerian Muslims and Christians in the country’s social, political and economic arena, where religion and its values are highly stressed in speech and writing than in real practice. From the behaviour of many religious Nigerians today, in both private and public lives, it is evident, that many do not uphold the values of justice, honesty, equity, faithfulness, trustworthiness etc. as their guiding principles.

There have been series of reported cases where many adherents of Islam and Christianity in Nigeria are found to be involved in some dubious and unethical practices such as, falsification of age and certificates, evading the payment of legitimate taxes, levies and utility bills, and other corrupt and unacceptable practices in work places. According to Familusi, a typical Nigerian does not want to pay electricity tariff if he or she has the opportunity; a worker who gets to his or her place of assignment at 9am may write 7:30am in the register; dates of birth are falsified, while many have different states of origin; also, ghost workers abound in many establishments. All these can only worsen the already terrible situation.²³ Some Nigerian citizens have even gone as far as conniving with foreign nationals to steal the resources of their fatherland, especially petroleum products and other natural resources within the country’s territorial water bodies. Every day we hear of citizens who join foreigners to steal the country’s crude oil. This action is a flagrant violation of the spirit of patriotism to the nation. It is important to note at this juncture that lack of patriotism retard the growth and development of any nation. Familusi citing Ayantayo observes that patriotism is necessary for national survival. It is what makes people

willing to place their country above themselves.²⁴ However, this is seriously lacking in the religious life of an average Nigerian.

More pathetic is the fact that there has been gross violation of oath of office or oath of allegiance to the nation by public officers. The practice of the doctrine of oath of office or allegiance which is meant to regulate socio-ethical relations between the leaders and the followers has everything to do with the religious virtue of covenant-keeping and accountability. This is so because the instrument with which it is administered is religious in all its forms. According to Ogunleye,

The religious concept of covenant was introduced into the Nigeria system of government in the form of oath of office which public officers have to swear in order to make them serve the public conscientiously. The oath of office, which can be administered by either a court or its delegate, involved pledging loyalty to perform faithfully the duties associated with the office. During this exercise, each person is allowed to swear an oath of office with the religious paraphernalia or cultic symbol of the religion one belongs to. The purpose for using these religious objects is that, as sacred objects, they were believed to have the potentials to instill fear in the people who swear by them. However, of all the leaders that have been taking oath of office, hardly can you see any one taking his oath of office in an indigenous way. They either take it in a Christian or Muslim way, knowing the nature of their God who will postpone judgment till judgment day while African gods are capable of instant action.²⁵

Many Christians and Muslims in the Nigerian public offices who take their oath of office with the Bible and the Quran have continued to violate the virtues of accountability, altruism, transparency, patriotism, justice, loyalty, faithfulness and honesty contained in their sacred scriptures that they are supposed to uphold and practice in both their public and private life. This is an indication that they are hypocritical in their religious beliefs and practices.

The most surprising episode of the neglect of moral values in the Nigerian tripartite religious heritage by their adherents and the preponderance of corruption in the country's socio-political, economic and religious sphere is the involvement of clergymen in the issue. Religious leaders from the three main religions in Nigeria have contributed immensely either by commission or omission to the problem of corruption and the increasing level of immorality in the country. According to Olanipekun,

The negligence of our religious leaders in telling the truth and preaching morals in contemporary time precipitates the cold attitude of the other members of the societies towards moral values. This is so evident in a place like Nigeria because it is so obvious that the more religious Nigerians are, the more immoral they seem to become. The fear of God is no longer reining. Instead, people are now worshipping money and material things within the purview of religion. Many pastors, imams and the traditional priests are now money conscious and no longer ready to say the truth especially when the morally perverted rich followers of theirs come to them.²⁶

In Nigeria today, some clergymen take pride in telling lies and deceiving their adherents' during sermons in order to acquire material wealth for self-aggrandizement. Some pastors, imams and traditional priests lack sincerity and integrity in their interactions and dealings. Some have continued to appear on newspaper headings for financial corruption and other unethical practices such as, sex scandal and ritual killings. It is imperative to note that one of the problems facing the Nigerian society today is the issue of 'get rich quick syndrome' that has found its way into the contemporary religious assemblies. This issue has continued to promote the desire for excessive materialism, lack of contentment and avarice among religious believers across the various faith traditions in the country. This trend has added a troubling twist to the problem of corruption and moral decadence in the Nigerian state.

Religious Ethical Values

Religious ethical values are the most indispensable factor for achieving Nigeria's quest for national integration. According to Akpenpuun in his book *Wanagenian Ethics*, religious ethics or principles of social ethics are the standard moral measurements against which an individual's character, conduct or behaviour, thought, attitudes, actions and relationships are assessed, evaluated and judged to be good or bad, right or wrong, correct or incorrect.²⁷ Fortunately, these religio-ethical values are inherent in the three major religions in Nigeria. Among the numerous ethical values taught and encouraged by the three major religions in Nigeria and also recognized by the nation's constitution are: discipline, loyalty, justice, accountability and honesty.

- i. Discipline: Discipline covers a wide range of idea such as self-respect, self-control, obedience, humility, patience, honesty etc. A disciplined society frowns at acts such as corruption, laziness, lawlessness, intolerance, idleness, disorder, division, inefficiency, poor attitudes to work among others.²⁸ Discipline in Nigeria's dominant religions and in the constitution teaches that Nigerians are supposed to possess utmost self-control especially as it concerns managing the nation's commonwealth.
- ii. Loyalty: This means truthfulness to one's duty or obligation. It entails a person answering allegiance to a cause, superior authorities or a country.²⁹ Christianity and the other religions teach that everyone must submit himself to the governing authorities, for there is no authority except that which God has established. The authorities that exist have been established by God.
- iii. Justice: The quality of being fair or reasonable in your actions. It connotes the idea of equitable distribution of resources and opportunities in a way that is devoid of cheating.³⁰
- iv. Accountability: It entails taking responsibility for your decisions or actions and the willingness to explain them when called upon. Accountability increases with the rise in responsibilities. It encourages hard work, initiative, efficiency and productivity.³¹
- v. Honesty: it is facet of moral character and denotes positive virtues such as integrity, trustworthiness, truthfulness, sincerity and fairness.³² Honest people are dependable and can be counted upon to honour their duties, obligations, promises and contracts.³³ The general perception out there is that religious people are honest people going by religious teachings.

These values are articulated by various religious bodies and to some extent recognized by the Nigeria's constitution has been worthy of national integration, development, security and peaceful existence of the country.

Religious Ethical Values and National Integration

Nigeria was created to bring about social solidarity, stability and progress. It was intended to be a nation where all citizens enjoy equal rights, freedom and welfare to pursue legitimate goals. However, the nation today is facing multiple crises that destroy the foundation of her corporate existence. This has brought unwarranted and untold hardship on her citizens and institutions.³³ Over the years, Nigerian government and people have attempted to use different approaches and methods to solve her challenges to no avail. This means the search for the problem with Nigeria is particularly but not exclusively related to the absence or under-utilization of religious ethical values. Describing the situation, Nkeonye says, "Really, the rate of corruption, bribery, indiscipline, immorality, cheating, idleness, drug addiction, armed robbery, smuggling, kidnapping and other vices have assumed alarming proportions. As it were, it seems that everything has simply ford upside down in order to negate and thwart the legitimate aspirations of common Nigerians."³⁴

Similarly, Chinua Achebe in his view says the problem of Nigeria is simply that of indiscipline and corruption by both religious citizens and leaders.³⁵ This then questions the integrity of Nigerians who confesses one religion or another. All that is needed for evil to triumph unabated is when good people remain silent. Wole Soyinka in his literary piece "The Man Died" says: the man died in all those who kept silent in the face of tyranny.³⁶ The more religious people who are trained by the ethical values of their various religions, which promise to be the moral visor of the society, choose to remain silent in the face of moral issues plaguing the country; the more Nigerians shall continue to edge closer to a life of servitude and servility.

Religious values if properly harnessed, remains a veritable tool that can foster national transformation and integration. Individual and societal actions if mirrored through the approval of religious values can bring about equity and justice provided the said values are properly integrated into national life. The assumption that Nigeria can climb the ladder of progress without recourse to religious ethical values is actually the cog in the wheel of development. The quicker Nigerian people and government understand and appreciate the necessity for developing and maximizing religious value for nation cohesion, the better.

According to Yamsat, Nigeria cannot attain national integration that would foster expected development and national transformation except the citizens acquire and demonstrate the required values and traits. And the leadership has to set the example for the masses to follow with much enthusiasm and success.³⁷ The statement is true to the extent that Nigerian leaders profess one form of religion or another making them the touch bearers of all that is moral at the various strata of leadership. Should they refuse to shine or dim their light, the all country will be plunged into steep darkness as the current reality seems to suggest. It goes without disputation that the Nigeria's dream of national integration, peace, unity and development can only come to reality with the internationalising the core religious ethical values that were adopted and enshrined in the National Anthem and the Pledge like honesty, obedience, loyalty, patriotism, peace, faithfulness, unity. Also, chapter two (2) section 23 of the 1999 Nigerian Constitution provides a list of national values fashioned after some elements of religious ethical values and renamed "Nigerian national ethics"; which are seven in number and listed as follows: discipline, integrity, dignity of labour, social justice, religious tolerance, patriotism and self-reliance.³⁸ These values are the compass or guide to human existence and corporation. They are the ideals which Nigerians must stand for and promote. These are worth living for and if necessary, worth dying for.

It is only appropriate at this point to return Nigeria to these core values because clearly, the problem bedevilling the nation today can be traced to the deficiency of moral values. Malomo categorically asserts that: "The perception of our ethical situation is that Nigeria is morally sick... our moral sickness is however, a unique product of certain unique internal predisposition and certain external morally pathogenic factors."³⁹ Indeed, Nigeria is a nation on the verge of collapse. Yamsat while describing the current state of the nation insists that:

Nothing appears to work straight as it is done elsewhere around the world. You have to know someone to climb up the ladder of success however knowledgeable and talented, whether pertaining the civil service, business, judiciary and schools for example. Excellency appears not to give anyone anything except who you know, where you come from or how much you have to give to get what you want. And if you are able to pay for it, you can do whatever you can; you will get away with it without the law going after you, even though the law is well documented and the enforcement agencies abound.⁴⁰

This is not to mention the gross perversion of justice and the senseless killings in form of cultism, banditry, kidnapping, herdsmen terrorism, armed robbery, political thuggery, and ritual killings. All these amounts to inhuman, unethical, evil and immoral acts which are not based on the interest of national integration, security, public safety, public order and public morality in a society as religious as Nigeria. The onus is on the religious peoples of Nigeria to arise and manifest those codes of conduct set out for them in their sacred books, in order to urgently save the nation from further damage and the risk of disintegration.

Recommendations

Everywhere one turns to, Nigerian children are being bombarded with a barrage of questions bordering on moral sensitivity whether from the school, the music they listen to, the movies and Television shows they watch, intense peer and internet pressure. Such influences can challenge their beliefs about what is right and what is wrong. As such, religious leaders and institutions must not relent in teaching and monitoring the internalization, transmission and utilization of religious ethical values in Nigeria. Again, since education without religious ethical values is futile and remains the bane of any progressive society, relevant stake-holders must do everything possible ranging from informal to formal sectors of education to inspire a new generation of people that will

appreciate religious values and save the nation from the embarrassment of an eminent collapse. The progressive values that respect the authentic dignity of the human person and promote discipline, loyalty, justice, accountability and honesty must be inculcated in the Nigerian child as early as possible while those that are preposterous to human growth and social justice should be disposed and consigned to the garbage of history. In a globalizing era where the key indicators of development have remained core to the process of national transformation, there is an urgent need to engage a robust framework for imbibing national values and ethics which are a derivative of religious ethical values to foster an egalitarian society, as well as ensure sustainable national integration and development.

Conclusion

It has been observed with dismay the steep decline in morals and values among religious adherents and the citizens of Nigeria across all faith and cultures, which is largely responsible for the corruption, violence and decadence being witnessed today at the family, community and national life of the country. The Nigerian state today is trapped in avoidable violence, crime, poverty, corruption and underdevelopment largely because too much attention has been paid on the superficial approach of religion than the actual practice that could influence behaviour and command followership. Adequate attention has not been paid by religious people to the decay in the society to which religious ethical values remains a recipe for attaining moral probity. It has been argued that religious ethical values if properly harnessed have the potentials to manifest every point of influence in the country's socio-economic and religio-political life. This means that the religious people of Nigeria face an uphill task to abide and promote their religious ethical teachings in order to bring about moral fitness in a decaying society, for guaranteed social cohesion. This will contravene the situation where religion is often used to create confusion or pacify people to achieve some parochial interest at the expense of the common good. Therefore, adhering to religious ethical values will not only bring about moral sanity but it will as well, ensure an axiological panacea to Nigeria's quest for sustainable development and national integration.

Endnotes

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